

The Eclipse, WWVB, SIDs, Thunderstorms and Earwigs

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The eclipse of 27 August 2017 was more than a visual event. It caused a disturbance in the ionosphere, changing propagation conditions of radio signals. Several of us “tuned in” to record any effect that may have occurred.

The Ionosphere

The ionosphere is a layer of the atmosphere that extends from about 40 miles above the earth to over 500 miles. The air up there is thin, but plays a vital role in the propagation of radio signals. At that elevation, ultraviolet and X-rays from the sun, as well as from other sources such as cosmic rays and thunderstorms, detach electrons from oxygen and nitrogen atoms, producing a *plasma* of positively-charged ions and free (negative) electrons.

The free electrons interact with the electric field of a radio signal and can either absorb it or re-radiate part of it back to earth.

The frequency of the radio signal strongly affects how it interacts with the free electrons: VHF and UHF signals oscillate too rapidly for the electrons to follow closely, and pass right through to outer space. Lower frequency signals can reflect or be absorbed, depending on the density of free electrons.

The ionization of the air atoms is a fairly rapid process, occurring in seconds or minutes, so it occurs early in the morning as the sun comes up. If the solar radiation is blocked by an eclipse, the plasma can rapidly recombine back into neutral atoms.

The ionosphere comprises several distinct layers, historically named the F layer, the strongest and farthest out, with the E and D layers closer to the earth. The F layer persists day and night, but the E and especially the D layers are produced during the day and then disappear at sunset.

Radio Station WWVB

WWVB is a 60 kHz radio station in Fort Collins, Colorado that transmits, 24 hours a day, a standard time and frequency signal. It’s what your “atomic” clock uses to set its own time. Propagation is by both groundwave and by skywave refracted off the ionized layers in the ionosphere.

During the day, the signal is both refracted off and absorbed by the D layer, and is usually quite stable. In fact, from day-to-day, the transmission time to the Bay Area is stable to around one microsecond consistency, measured at two points in time separated by 24 hours. Between sunset and the following sunrise, when the D layer disappears, the signal refracted off the E and F layers is much stronger, but due to the varying conditions, mainly due to thunderstorms around the world, the signal strength and propagation time can be strongly varying. In the Bay Area, multipath diffraction causes strong signal amplitude variation around sunrise and sunset.

As the daytime strength and propagation time of WWVB during the day are quite stable, measuring these parameters during the eclipse and comparing them to a baseline measurement taken over several

days or weeks can give a picture of the changes in the ionosphere due to the partial blocking of sunlight during the eclipse.

The Eclipse

This once-in-a-lifetime event occurred 21 August 2017, sweeping from the Northwest to the Southeast of the United States. In the Bay Area, we experienced a 76% reduction in sunlight at 10:40 AM PDT (UTC-7). The Bay Area and WWVB are both on the same side of the path of totality, but one would expect that even so, some changes would occur in the ionosphere. Those living east of the Berkeley-Oakland hills actually had an opportunity to see partial totality; all we in the Bay Area saw were clouds and overcast.

Receivers

In Berkeley, I measured both the amplitude and time shift of the 60 kHz WWVB carrier.

The amplitude was measured by receiving the signal in a tuned loop antenna followed by amplifiers and a tuned Collins-Telettra RF voltmeter that was calibrated to give the signal strength at the antenna in units of microvolts per meter at the amplitude modulation peak.

The time shift of the 60 kHz carrier was measured by a Fluke 207-5 carrier phase tracking receiver, using an independent amplified 1-meter whip antenna, locked to a stable GPS time reference. The time shift of the carrier is measured relative to the GPS reference. The binary phase shift time code modulation of the signal that prevents phase lock was removed using a “dephaser” so that the tracking receiver could phase lock onto the 60 kHz signal.

Both the amplitude and time shifts were sampled 20 times a second, and each minute 1200 of those samples were integrated and recorded. As the signal contains both amplitude and phase modulation, the long sampling time integrated out the 17 dB time code modulation, and the amplitude normalization represents the peak amplitude of the signal.

A baseline of the amplitude and signal timing was taken over a period of four weeks of continuous recording by a Raspberry Pi 3B microcomputer using two channels of a 10-bit MCP3008 ADC to convert the analog amplitude and phase signals to a digital data stream.

What I Saw

Previous data from others of receiving a VLF signal during an eclipse show no general trend other than the signal strength could be either greater or less during the eclipse. That indicates that multipath propagation is partly responsible for changes in signal strength.

The eclipse came and went, and I saw a small “blip” in the signal amplitude (the black curve) for 21 August, centered around 10:40 PM PDT.

This figure shows the amplitude record of WWVB in Berkeley for a 1-week interval from 15 August 2017 to 21 August. Each 24-hour daily interval is overlaid on the same horizontal axis with units of hours Pacific Daylight Time (UTC-7), and the absolute signal strength shown on the vertical axis in units of microvolts per meter electric field strength at the modulation peak.

Note a dramatic signal strength drop around 5:15 and 19:45, approximately the sunrise and sunset times in Berkeley. The signal strength is much higher at night, and shows significant variability. Also note that the receiving equipment saturates at 1000 microvolts per meter.

During the day, the signal strength range is 200-400 microvolts per meter and very repeatable.

At 10:40 PDT the eclipse was at its maximum in Berkeley. Note the small “blip” around 10:40 PDT. Normally, the signal strength at that time is about 280 microvolts per meter. However, starting a little later than 9 AM, the signal strength dropped to 200 microvolts per meter, and then did a quick upswing and downswing at 10:40, returning to its usual value by noon. I can only attribute this to interference due to multipath, and another near observer might see something else.

Note also the signal strength blips on 18-20 August. These are due to SIDs.

The plot below shows the relative time shift of the WWVB carrier in units of microseconds, referred to a GPS time reference. As with the signal strength, between sunrise and sunset the phase of the received carrier repeats within a microsecond each day, and is quite erratic after dark. The time variation during the eclipse is the strong dip centered around 10:40 PDT.

The time variation was quite dramatic, approaching the day-night time shift of several tens of microseconds when the D layer disappears. The signal during the eclipse was delayed 39 microseconds from its baseline value at 10:40 PDT, indicating an increase in path length of 11.7 km, or 7.3 miles, due to the partial disappearance of the D layer and the signal refracting from the higher E layer during the partial eclipse.

Sudden Ionospheric Disturbances (SIDs)

The amplitude and carrier shift plots for the dates of 18-20 August 2017 show sudden increases in signal strength and positive shifts in carrier phase. These are due to bursts of X-rays and ultraviolet radiation from the sun that increases the ionization level of the D-layer.

Increased ionization of the D-layer lowers the plane of reflection of the 60 kHz, effectively shortening the path length therefore advancing the phase of the received signal. Thus the sign of the time shift is opposite that of the eclipse event, where the D-layer ionization level is temporarily reduced.

The signal strength is also increased during the SIDs events.

The plot at the right is a record of the solar X-ray flux recorded by the GOES13 satellite, and the peaks correspond to the observations.

Antenna Work at WWVB Sensed

The plot below shows the carrier time shift record of WWVB from 17 June 2016 through 21 June, over the mid-day time span, as a function of a fraction of a decimal day (1.0, 2.0 = midnight, 1.5 = noon). (Each plot is displaced upward by 0.5 microsecond for clarity.) On the 20th (yellow line) an anomaly, starting about 7:20 AM PDT and lasting two hours shows a 0.8 microsecond advance in signal phase. What was that?

At that time, I speculated that the 0.8 microsecond offset looked too constant or the wrong time scale to be caused by a meteor or CME, so is it from an event at WWVB itself? The station uses two top-loaded vertical antennas, 875 meters apart, each with its own transmitter, radiating a total of 50 kW.

The two antennas are sited on a bearing line of 145 degrees. The effective center of the signal phase is located midway between the two antennas.

If the south (farther) transmitter ceases transmission for a trip condition or for maintenance, the phase center of the origin of the signal moves 251 meters closer to Berkeley, as it is now radiating from the north (nearer) antenna. The motion of the effective transmitting location 251 meters closer to Berkeley would result in a positive time shift of 0.84 microseconds, close to the observed value of 0.8 microsecond. Is this what happened?

The mystery was solved when Matt Deutch of NIST responded to an inquiry with:

Howdy John,
We did indeed have a problem. 2:13 p.m. PDT or 2113 UTC an intense thunderstorm passed over and we had 40 mph wind gust and what appears to be a direct hit from lightning. We were completely off the air for about 2 hrs and 10 minutes. Right after I restored the WWVB broadcast at 2325 UTC we were at about 60% power as the transmitters warmed up. I turned up the power later and we should have been at full power by 0000 UTC.

You will be happy to know that your "wild speculation" was right on the money. I looked back in the records and we did do maintenance on our south antenna on that date.

Matt

Earwigs

Things don't always go right. During the one-month baseline run, some anomalies started appearing in the amplitude record. The measured signal strength would lessen, but when the power to the equipment was cycled, the strength would come back up to normal.

The photo shows the loop antenna on a mast, suspended below the rotator, with the head-end preamplifier in the nearby enclosure.

After all other possible causes were eliminated, the head-end preamp was demounted and opened up, showing a family of earwigs taking up residence. The preamp circuit includes a high input impedance FET first stage, and a small leakage from a resident insect could alter the bias of the first amplifier. The warmth of the components could have attracted the insects, who may have moved away when the power was cut.

Cleaning and reinstalling the preamp enclosure cured the problem.

Appendix

Some additional details of the receiver and data logger follow.

The WWVB data logging system comprises separate amplitude and phase channels, feeding analog data into an ADC and minicomputer.

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The phase monitor channel comprises an E-field 1-meter whip antenna on the end of the ham shack feeding a narrow-band 60 kHz amplifier whose output is leveled by a slow-responding AGC system.

The WWVB signal format contains time information encoded in two ways: by amplitude modulation of the carrier and by a bi-phase shift keying (BPSK), where the phase of the carrier is flipped by 180 degrees for each code bit. This phase shift prevents a phase-lock loop from locking onto an average carrier phase, which is required to determine long-term carrier time shifts.

One technique to recover absolute carrier time shifts is to remove the BPSK modulation by mixing the carrier with itself, doubling its frequency to 120 kHz, so 180 degree phase jumps become 360 degrees, indistinguishable from zero degrees. The

output of the multiplier is 120 kHz, which is heterodyned with a GPS-derived 100 kHz carrier to produce a mixer product of 20 kHz, which is within the tuning range of the Fluke 207-5 tracking receiver.

The signal amplitude is measured by receiving the signal with a 90-turn 1-meter diameter loop antenna. The resonant frequency of the loop is 78 kHz, and the loop gain is calculated from first principles from its geometry. When the loop is tuned to 60 kHz by a shunt capacitor, a 4.7 dB increase in signal strength is obtained. The loop is followed by a cascade of two preamplifiers, one at the loop, and one inside the ham shack, each with a gain of 20 dB at 60 kHz.

The signal strength is measured with a Collins-Telettra dual-conversion RF voltmeter, covering a frequency range of 4 to 750 kHz, with an IF output frequency of 15 kHz. The RF voltmeter IF output is followed by a linear RF-to-DC converter, the resulting DC level proportional to the received signal amplitude.

The data logger comprises a Raspberry Pi 3B running Ubuntu Linux 15.10. A MCP3008 8-channel 10-bit ADC is directly coupled to the 40-pin GPIO connector using a serial peripheral interface bus communications protocol. Only four connections to the Pi are required: chip select, clock, data input and data output. A driver was written in C that has the calling format:

```
unsigned int readadc(int input_channel, int clock_pin, int mosi_pin, int miso_pin, int cs_pin)
```

that produces a 10-bit integer value of the input voltage at the specified input channel.

Each of the two analog inputs (amplitude and carrier phase) is sampled 20 times a second; each minute 1200 samples are averaged to one value and written to a time-stamped log file. These log files are further analyzed and displayed in a spreadsheet.

A full month of data was accumulated to establish a baseline for the diurnal amplitude and phase variations.

The Author

Dr. John Staples, W6BM, designs and builds particle accelerators at the Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory. He received his Extra Class ham license and First Class Radiotelephone and Radar licenses in 1958. Besides being an avid collector of vintage electronics, he has been a passionate motorcyclist for over 50 years.

